

NAME: Kristine Hildebrandt

DATE COMPLETED: Sept-Oct 2003

LG/LID: 206 Nepali

SOURCE(S): Acharya, Jayaraj. 1991. A descriptive grammar of Nepali and an analyzed corpus. Washington D.C.: Georgetown University Press.

SAVE AS RTF (RICH TEXT)

Revised Word Questionnaire (Oct 2003)

Depending on the structure of the language, you may need to consult the questions in a reversed order (e.g. look at stress patterns before looking at phonological rules of assimilation, etc.)

For assistance with terms you can consult Bickel's Programm und Verzeichnis der verfügbaren Materialien (on the server)

Or, refer to the .pdf version of the Bickel & Nichols chapter on inflectional morphology (<http://www.uni-leipzig.de/%7ebickel/research/papers/index.html>)

PHONETIC & PHONOLOGICAL QUESTIONS

- You should note forms that the author overtly *describes* (and also covertly *treats*) as phonologically independent. I am especially interested in the *crucial* differences between what is possible (or highly common) within a phonologically independent unit and what is possible at the *edges* or across boundaries
- As you investigate, make an inventory-style comparison of patterns/processes that apply to independent forms with both lexical content and grammatical content. Note what is possible within the form's internal boundaries versus what is possible at the edges (especially is the form is polysyllabic). For example, note possible and required consonant onsets at the initial edge of an independent unit, and compare these to the same onset patterns within the unit.
- If an author says something like "no final consonants" or "no consonants in final position", always check to see if this constraint holds up at syllable edges *within* a phonologically independent form, and at the *ending* edge of the form itself.
- Note also that a form may be phonologically "free" or independent, while not necessarily constituting a lexical category (i.e. "noun" or "verb" or "adjective"). I am especially interested in grammatical forms that are phonologically independent (and also lexical forms that are phonologically dependent upon something else—cannot occur alone phonologically, but they express a meaning that you might otherwise think of as "word")
- Always take from the grammar at least 1 useful example of each thing.
- Look for contradictory or conflicting phenomena (e.g. stress pattern A applies in almost all cases except...). This may be important. In some larger phonological units, one criterion may apply, but the other may suggest a different organization of units.

1. Segmental & Phonotactic Patterns (edges vs. internal)

--occurrence of segments, limitations, prohibitions

--voicing, aspiration patterns

--manner patterns (plosive, affricate, fricative, tap, approx, etc.)

--place (either specific like bilabial, lamino-dental, or general like anterior, coronal, etc.)

-- gemination

--vowel height/backness (quality)

--nasal vowels (see "rules")

-- vowel length

--VV sequences (includes diphthongs)

--idiosyncratic, segment-specific restrictions or possibilities, like "no labiodental approximants at starting edge, even though they occur medially etc."

Many word-final restrictions:

final ch, kh, r dispreferred

most final aspirated consonants de-aspirated

voiceless aspirated stops generally realized as voiced in word-medial position

Only CC's allowed at either word-start or end are CJ clusters. Word-medial CC are resyllabified (C.C)

No word-final geminates

#CCj clusters undergo various processes (vowel epenthesis with default vowel (CVCj); metathesis)

2. "Rules" Part 1

Some phonological processes are restricted in application to the internal domain of a phonologically independent unit, and others are restricted to the boundaries/edges. Sometimes these differences are explicitly noted, others may be implicit. Please list the major processes that highlight such boundaries. Do these things happen to lexical forms only, to grammatical forms only, or to both?

Note types and locations of:

--vowel/consonant HARMONY/assimilation/dissimilation (note the types—place, manner, voicing, other)

--segment DELETION/epenthesis, any kind of insertion/deletion processes

--segment METATHESIS or any type of re-ordering

3. "Rules" Part 2

Some rules referring to possible (and prohibited) syllable structures, processes of syllabification, and also to suprasegmental processes are sensitive to the domain of a phonologically independent unit. The distribution of these processes may help to define the boundaries and internal composition of such units.

Note:

--THE DEFAULT syllable template, and whether or not this template applies to the edges of phonologically free units. For example, a language may allow C clusters in coda position, but this may only happen at the ending edge of a phon. free unit, and not internally (or the other way around)

--C COMBOS—are the same types permitted both internally and at edges?

--syllabification patterns (across syllables internally, vs. across morphemes, vs. across independent units)

--SUPER heavy syllables (Hall 2001). Can something that is phonologically free end with a super-heavy syllable? Or can such syllables only be in an internal position? What are the types (e.g. CV:C; CVVC: CVCC)? Can all types occur *anywhere* in a phon. free unit? Note even any seemingly idiosyncratic restrictions (like, might a certain suffix never co-occur with a SHS?, etc.)

$C(Cj)V(:)(Cj)(C)$

No minimal word-requirements: V and CV are both permitted and frequent

*SHS—CCjV:C# (monosyllabics only) /pwaal/ 'hole'
maybe CVCjC? /cayt/ 'april-may months'*

--STRESS It might be a good idea to look at stress rules first, as these can often clearly illuminate boundaries of phonologically free units—especially if the language only allows "1 main stress per word" or something of that nature. You can then work "backwards" and look at other cues to independent status.

--is there a primary stress rule? what is the domain?

--what types of forms are included, what is exempted?

--what are the minimal/maximal domains for stress to apply? Can a phonologically free unit that is simply (C)V take the main stress?

--can only lexical forms take a main stress, or can independent grammatical forms also take it?

Stress is not phonemic in Nepali, but stress properties are observed.

Most frequent pattern on polysyllabic stems & roots: primary stress on initial syllable

Alternate pattern: if there is a non-initial syllable with the following syllable structure:

/VCj/, /VnVn/ (where n is nasalization on the vowel), /e/ or /o/ (/e/ and /o/ are phonetically much longer ("extra long") than other vowels in Nepali)

and that syllable is immediately adjacent to the initial syllable,

and the initial syllable is only /i, u, a/, or /in, un, an/ (where the n=nasalization on the vowel)

then the heavier non-initial syllable takes the primary stress.

So:

most frequent pattern:

/ˈka:ka:/ 'uncle'

/ˈba.sa/ ‘sit down (imp.)’
/ˈcha.ya:/ ‘shadow’
/ˈdar.ba:r/ ‘palace’

alternate pattern:

/pa.ˈka:un.cha/ ‘cook.3sg.pres’
no data for other types

but note the more frequent pattern for:

/ˈbhak.bha.ka:un.cha/ ‘stutter.3sg.pres’

Because even though there is an extra-heavy syllable, it is not immediately adjacent to the initial syllable, so the initial syllable still takes primary stress.

Overall then, the initial syllable is favored in most situations, regardless of the number/type of bound morphemes.

Both phonological words and suffixes may show “emphatic stress”—so on suffixes, this appears to defy the regular stress pattern. The phonetic result of emphatic stress on suffixes is either [v:] or [v?] (glottal stop)

--TONE Again, another good starting place if other cues are hard to find. Is the domain of tone a syllable? morpheme? phonologically free unit? If the language has syllabic tone, there may still be a word-level domain at work, like "only 1 high per phon. free unit" or something else like this. If grammatical forms take tone, do they also have other features that might suggest that they can stand alone phonologically (like the other stuff listed above)?

--"PITCH ACCENT" In some languages, the apparent tonal contrasts are not clearly defined until they occur on a "larger" unit. Describe the morphological and/or syllabic complexities of such units

4. Minimality & Maximality

Look at the grammar, look also at the dictionary/glossary entries if they are included. What is the most common (or only) minimal and maximal size of a phon. free unit? Or alternatively, what is the minimal/maximal morphological complexity/composition of something that is phonologically free? (C)V? CV (with an initial crucially present)? di- or polysyllable? How big can a free unit be in terms of syllable number? Do these size constraints apply only to lexical forms? If there are constraints, must a lexical form be bimorphemic to be free? If so, what morphemes qualify? Any & all?

5. Reduplication

Is the entire unit copied? More? Less? Can something of any phonological size/complexity have reduplication (even if the process is semantically restricted)? If there are different *types* of reduplication, see if you can find patterns, or note what the author says.

Is the resulting suprasegmental pattern of a reduplicated form the same or different from a single free form? (Are there 2 main stresses or 1? 2 tones? a different tone altogether?)

6. Other Questions

Note any discussion & descriptions of phonological boundaries attributed to interruption or pause phenomena. Also note if the author argues for boundaries because of repair phenomena. Examples. Only in the more detailed grammars will you probably see such discussions.

7. Phonological Units in Morphologically Complex Forms

--COMPOUNDING: note any patterns of segmental alteration with compounds—especially at the edges of compounds; note prior and resulting stress/tone patterns; note segmental restrictions in compounds (e.g. in Manange, the 2nd element may never have an aspirated onset, even if the onset of the form when it is free is aspirated).

Again, note any conflicts of properties (e.g. in Lhasa Tibetan, a compound has 2 tone contours, but there is vowel harmony that spreads across the entire compound, and only a single main stress)

Sometimes in a compound, a piece of one of the elements may be deleted. If this happens, note any patterns, because this may suggest that one of the elements is in fact not a single phonological unit.

Compound is one pword: the resulting word carries primary stress only on the initial syllable, with one and only one primary stress in the compound word (no discussion as to whether alternate stress rule applies)

--"SIMPLE juxtaposition or concatenation of 2+ independent forms"—these are things that might be called "serialization" in some grammars: note any phonological discussion of these things. single tone? single stress? segment changes? ordering restrictions? co-occurrence restrictions?

--MULTI-morphemic forms: this is already discussed in above sections, but note especially phonologically free units that are minimally bimorphemic (or bigger), note any allomorphy that suggests that multi-morphemic forms behave as a single phonological unit.

--IF a language has a wide variety of inflectional affixes, do all stem-affix combinations have the same/similar stress, syllabification, segmental patterns, phon rules, tones, etc? Describe those that deviate from the set "general" patterns. Give examples. In German, for example, a stem + certain suffixes behaves as a **single** phonological unit ([li:.bɪ] 'love 1.sg'), but a stem + certain other suffixes behaves as **2** phonological units ([li:p.liç] 'dearly')—the resyllabification & voicing of the plosive is evidence of this.

Be sensitive to exceptions/variations in segmental/phonotactic, prosodic rules that may suggest that certain things "go together" phonologically, and others that do not. Explicitly state the conditions under which variations apply.

MORPHOLOGY & SYNTAX QUESTIONS

The goal here is to identify individual grammatical forms (or combinations of forms) as independent units (grammatical units/grammatical words). In some cases, these forms (or combinations of) exist as syntactic units, at other times as morphological units. Still other times, the distinctions will be collapsed or blurred. The primary interest here is not whether or not they are phonologically independent, although it is important to note whether or not the things you're describing are free or bound. This is because we will be creating a 3rd dedicated database that charts the overlaps/alignments between things that are phonologically free and things that are morpho-syntactically free.

8. Create a (glossed) list of inflectional morphemes (the types) described. Note the distribution of each morpheme:

--with what **MUST** they co-occur (bound or free)?

--with what else **MAY** they (optionally) co-occur (bound or free)?

--if they co-occur with multiple different types of forms (either as a host or attached to a host), are the resulting meanings always the same, or are they different? Note the differences with examples.

--can other elements ever be inserted between morpheme forms that comprise a stem + infl. form unit? See if adverbs can do this.

9. Note the overall constituent ordering patterns in the language. Is the pattern rigid, somewhat fluid, very fluid? Do all inflectional/grammatical elements that are called "free" follow the same ordering possibilities as lexical elements? Do they consistently appear in a single ordering scheme or co-occurrence scheme despite being phonologically independent. Pay special attention to so-called particles, or other minimally free forms.

10. Does the author discuss grammatical forms/combinations with a conventionalized meaning or coherence? In other words, are there grammatical combinations with 1 meaning, and that meaning is lost or irretrievable (or totally different) when a piece of the form is missing or when the form is analyzed piece-by-piece? "Constructions" might be a way that grammarians describe this.

11. Are there elements with some degree of ordering or grammatical freedom, but that seem to be phonologically bound? Describe their distribution. Are there elements that appear to be phonologically independent (see above criterion), but have a fixed order or co-occurrence constraint? Describe these too. Pay special attention to things the author calls clitics.

12. Is a grammatical unit always bigger than a single morpheme? Always the same size? Are there some grammatical units that are a single morpheme, but others that are combinations? What is the biggest possible grammatical unit in the language (in terms of numbers of morphemes), and what is the smallest? Pay attention to, for example, the NP, and then also the elements that make up the NP. Then, note the predicate, and then the things that make up the predicate (may be called the "verbal complex").

13. Looking at the main verbal complex in the grammar, how morphologically complex is it?

Looking at the predicate of the clause, how many verbs or verb-like elements must be present? verb-only? verb + aux form? 2 + verbs? If aux forms appear, is there a minimal amount (like, there must be at least 1 aux), or is there a maximal amount (like, there can be no more than 3...). In English, for example, in the predicate, there can be just 1 verb (=gword), but there can maximally be up to 1 verb plus 3 or so other gword forms (auxiliaries plus the main verb). (degree of synthesis)

QUESTION: Do we want students to note the degree of fusion and flexivity of things they describe? the terms themselves (in my thinking) already assume that the forms are a single (morphologically complex) grammatical word.

concatenative-nonflexive

concatenative-flexive

isolating-flexive

non-concatenative-non-flexive

(isolating non-flexive?)—phon free with allomorphy driven by morpho-phonology

these things already have existing definition files

Do we want to list individual items across languages that can be grammatical words

aspect markers a, b, c in lg X = 1 gword

aspect markers d & e are not gwords themselves

lexical nouns in lg x = 1 gword

pronouns in lg x are not gwords

markers of case are gwords

or

Do we want to have simpler, larger-scale categories and label them as either +/- gw

for ex: the predicate in English is optionally several gwords, the verbal complex is only 1gword or both of these?

How to fit in questions that direct the investigators towards noting both synword and gword, where:

synword defined by terminal node/min. projection, syntactic dependencies

gword defined more by co-occurrence, ordering, coherence/cohesiveness

Other things we want to include, but I'm not sure how to fit them into "gword" thinking (or maybe they belong more with pword):

--bi-partite stems (maybe just note them and any phonological stuff)

--non-adjacent allomorphy

--clause-changing/converbs (perhaps both gword & pword)

--certain (but not all) derivational operations